

Task Aware Impedance Planning

Liana Bertoni

University of Pisa / HHCM

Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia
Genoa, Italy

liana.bertoni@iit.it

Luca Muratore

HHCM

Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia
Genoa, Italy

luca.muratore@iit.it

Arturo Laurenzi

HHCM

Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia
Genoa, Italy

arturo.laurenzi@iit.it

Nikos Tsagarakis

HHCM

Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia
Genoa, Italy

nikos.tsagarakis@iit.it

Abstract—Robots in realistic environments require the capability of adapting themselves to different conditions and task requirements regarding motion tracking performances, interaction forces, and payload conditions. Therefore, an online impedance modulation during the task execution represents a critical prerequisite for the robots operating in real-world environments, remaining an open research topic today. This work presents a novel task-based online impedance modulation with stability online verified. The method allows modulating the robot impedance following the task requirements. The method considers the motion tracking performance requested by the task and the expected task payload or interaction forces to derive the robot impedance. Appropriate impedance levels are also maintained to ensure the stability of the modulated robot impedance. The method is successfully verified on the CENTAURO robot.

I. INTRODUCTION

The effective use of robots in realistic environments demands the capability of adapting themselves to different conditions and tasks to execute. Based on that, a compliant strategy may be attained to achieve the required flexibility.

From its initial studies [1], impedance has demonstrated to be an effective tool in facilitating the robot flexibility concerning the task execution, physical interaction and uncertainties [2], [3], and [4]. Online and variable impedance modulation appears to be beneficial for the robotic system. Examples can be seen in [5] - [8]. Nevertheless, the selection of impedance parameters, as well as their online modulation is still an open problem in the research community.

Since online impedance modulation can simplify the achievement of tasks requirements defined as motion precision, forces and payload settings, while remaining compliant as much as possible, in this work, a novel online impedance modulation strategy based on the task requirements is proposed. In detail, the developed method explores the motion tracking performance request by the task and the expected payload (or interaction forces) during the task execution. An effective stiffness at the Cartesian level is accordingly derived and properly used to compute the robot impedance. The stability of the generated motion is thus online verified. The method is validated through a number of experiments performed with the CENTAURO Robot [9], fig. 2. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II provides the problem statement, Section III reports the details of the impedance modulation method, while Section IV discusses

the stability analysis, Section V discusses the experiments performed to validate the method and Section VI addresses the conclusion.

II. TASK-BASED ONLINE IMPEDANCE MODULATION DESIGN

A. Preliminaries

A fully actuated articulated robot with n joints can be described by the following model:

$$M(q)\ddot{q} + C(q, \dot{q})\dot{q} + G(q) = \tau + J(q)^T w_{ext} \quad (1)$$

where $q, \dot{q}, \ddot{q} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ are joints position, velocity, and acceleration vectors of the robot, $M(q) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ represents the inertia matrix, $C(q, \dot{q}) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ represents the Coriolis term, $G(q) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the gravity vector, $\tau \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the joints torque as a input, $J(q) \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times n}$ is the Jacobian matrix of the end-effector of the robot, and $w_{ext} \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the external wrench. In this model, the matrix $C(q, \dot{q})$ can be chosen such that $\dot{M}(q) = C(q, \dot{q}) + C(q, \dot{q})^T$ holds, and having $\dot{M}(q) - 2C(q, \dot{q}) = 0$. The control law used to command the robot is a proportional-derivative (PD) control law with gravity and external wrench compensation as shown below

$$\tau = K_J(t)(q_d - q) - D_J(t)\dot{q} + \tau_g + \tau_{ext} \quad (2)$$

where $q_d \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the desired joints position vector, $\tau_g \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the gravity torque vector, $\tau_{ext} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the torque generated by the external wrench acting on the robot ($\tau_{ext} = J(q)^T w_{ext}$), $K_J(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $D_J(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ are the varying (diagonal) joints stiffness and damping matrices.

B. Task-Based Online Impedance Modulation Design

Considering a Cartesian task with requirements of a desired task error $\Delta x_{ee}^{t,d} \in \mathbb{R}^6$, and a desired task wrench $w_{ee}^{t,d} \in \mathbb{R}^6$, to accomplish the task and meet the requirements by modulating the impedance of the robot, a virtual spring is attached to the robot end-effector and the desired Cartesian stiffness (chosen diagonal) $K_C^d = \text{diag}\{k_c^d\} \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 6}$ is set in the following manner

$$K_C^d = \frac{|w_{ee}^d|}{\Delta x_{ee}^d}, \quad (3)$$

where $w_{ee}^d \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the desired wrench and $\Delta x_{ee}^d \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the desired error, both at the end-effector.

The desired wrench is given by a model-based gravity component $w_g \in \mathbb{R}^6$, and an external component $w_{ext} \in \mathbb{R}^6$

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the Task Aware Online Impedance Modulation.

representing the expected payload or interaction force to be supported and/or applied. The desired task wrench is modeled as an external wrench ($w_{ext} = w_{ee}^{t,d}$). Consequently, the desired wrench is computed as a sum: $w_{ee}^d = w_g + w_{ext}$.

The desired error is designed in such a way to have the robot compliant as much as possible. Therefore, the desired error profile is computed as below

$$\Delta x_{ee}^d = d(t) \cdot \Delta x_{ee}^{initial} + (1 - d(t)) \cdot \Delta x_{ee}^{t,d}, \quad (3a)$$

$d(t) = \frac{d(t)^{actual}}{d^{initial}}$, where $x^{initial} \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the initial error (design parameter), $d(t)^{actual} \in \mathbb{R}$ is the distance of the final pose (target) from the actual pose of the end-effector, $d^{initial} \in \mathbb{R}$ is the initial distance of the end-effector from the final pose and then $d(t) \in \mathbb{R}$ is a value from 0 to 1. The desired Cartesian stiffness is realized by the robot as [10]

$$K_J(t) = J(q)^T K_C^d J(q) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}, \quad (4)$$

with ($\frac{\partial J(q)^T}{\partial q} K_C^d \Delta x_{ee} = 0$). The varying joint damping is then derived in accordance with the level of the joint stiffness [11]

$$D_J(t) = 2\xi \sqrt{K_J(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}, \quad (5)$$

$\xi \in \mathbb{R}$ is the damping ratio to be defined. Finally, to realize the derived joint stiffness and damping matrices required to satisfy the task requirements, (4) and (5), we directly implement the diagonal elements of these matrices in a decentralized manner at the local joint controllers of the joints. The *off*-diagonal terms of the joints stiffness and damping matrices are realized by computing the appropriate feed-forward torque terms in the decentralized controllers as in [12].

C. Stability Analysis

For the system provided in (1), (2) with the proposed joint online impedance (stiffness and damping) modulation, equations (4) and (5), we use the Lyapunov direct method [13] to prove the stability. For a given q_d , the error vectors, $\bar{q} = q - q_d$, $\dot{\bar{q}} = \dot{q} - \dot{q}_d$ and $\ddot{\bar{q}} = \ddot{q} - \ddot{q}_d$ can be introduced. Assuming that $K_J(t)$ and $D_J(t)$ are time-varying and at

least semi-positive definite, we choose the following Lyapunov candidate function

$$V(\bar{q}, \dot{\bar{q}}, t) = \frac{1}{2} \dot{\bar{q}}^T M(q) \dot{\bar{q}} + \frac{1}{2} \bar{q}^T K_J(t) \bar{q}, \quad (6)$$

with $V(\bar{q}, \dot{\bar{q}}, t) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ positive definite, ($V(\bar{q}, \dot{\bar{q}}, t) > 0$) to proof the stability of our system. The stability of the system is satisfied if the derivative of the Lyapunov candidate function is at least semi-negative definite ($\dot{V}(\bar{q}, \dot{\bar{q}}, t) \leq 0$). Therefore, the stability condition is given as follows

$$\dot{\bar{q}}^T D_J(t) \dot{\bar{q}} \geq \frac{1}{2} \bar{q}^T \dot{K}_J(t) \bar{q}. \quad (7)$$

D. Ensuring Stability

To fulfill the stability condition provided in (7), the joint stiffness and damping may need to be adjusted. Using the property of the quadratic form, the stability condition can be reduced as below

$$\lambda_{min}(D_J(t)) \|\dot{\bar{q}}\|^2 \geq \frac{1}{2} \lambda_{max}(\dot{K}_J(t)) \|\bar{q}\|^2, \quad (8)$$

and rearranging, we have

$$\lambda_{min}(D_J(t)) \geq \lambda_{min,D_J}^{stable} \quad (9)$$

with $\lambda_{min,D_J}^{stable} = \lambda_{max}(\dot{K}_J(t)) \frac{\|\bar{q}\|^2}{2\|\dot{\bar{q}}\|^2}$. If the computed joint damping as provided in (5) violates this constraint, the joint damping is adjusted as below

$$\bar{D}_J(t) = 2\xi \sqrt{K_J(t)} + \Delta_{D_J} I \quad (10)$$

where $I \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the identity matrix and $\Delta_{D_J} = \lambda_{min}^{stable} - \lambda_{min}(D_J(t)) \in \mathbb{R}$ is the minimum value required to ensure the stability condition. Given a maximum joints damping available, $D_J^{max} = \text{diag}\{d_j^{max}\} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, if required, the joint damping is increased until its maximum, and the stability condition is ensured by acting on the joints stiffness. Then,

$$\lambda_{max}(\dot{K}_J(t)) \leq \lambda_{max,K_J}^{stable} \quad (11)$$

with $\lambda_{max,K_J}^{stable} = \lambda_{min}(D_J^{max}) \frac{2\|\dot{\bar{q}}\|^2}{\|\bar{q}\|^2}$. The joint stiffness $K^{stable}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is therefore determined in order to realize the stiffness derivative of the joint that ensures the

stability condition (11). Summarizing, the proposed variable impedance modulation, which also ensures the stability of the system, is determined as follows

$$K_s(t) = \begin{cases} K_J(t) & \text{if (8) or (9) is satisfied} \\ K^{stable}(t) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Similarly for the damping,

$$D_s(t) = \begin{cases} D_J(t) & \text{if (8) is satisfied} \\ \bar{D}_J(t) & \text{if (9) is satisfied} \\ D^{max} & \text{neither (8) nor (9) is satisfied} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Fig. 1 provides an overview of the proposed method.

III. EXPERIMENTS

To demonstrate and validate the proposed online impedance modulation method, a set of experiments were performed. In particular a drilling task with two different executions.

A. Experimental Setup

Drilling task: This task involves the drilling of a concrete masonry unit. The task has been executed with two different motion velocities but with the same desired task error along the x direction equal to $0.03m$ for both, while the other directions were set equal to $0.06m$ (y -axis), and $0.04m$ (z -axis), respectively. The force required to execute the drilling task has been roughly estimated by some trials and set equal to $200N$ along the x directing. The setup is shown in figure 2. The initial error ($x_{ee}^{initial}$) has been chosen equal to $0.10m$. The tasks have been performed with a joint damping ratio in (5) equal to $\xi = 0.7$. The reference frame used to express the Cartesian quantities is the frame attached to the torso of the robot, F_{torso} as shown in Fig. 2.

The execution of the experiment is explained below. The drilling task immediately starts to move towards the x direction. An end-effector force estimation module, which utilizes the joint torque measurements on the robot arm, is used to detect the contact of the drill bit. At that time, the robot stops to move and a transition phase starts where the wrench at end-effector is smoothly increased to the level desired and specified by the drilling task. Once, this phase is finished, the robot continues to move while the impedance is modulated as described in section II, and the stability checked as detailed in sub-section II-D.

B. Experimental Results

The results from the task performed are discussed below. *Drilling task:* In the plots, figure 3, the contact detection is highlighted with the blue and light blue bold dashed lines for the two drilling experiment trials. Due to the different velocity of the trajectory in the two experiments, the contact is detected at different times. In these experiments, the threshold for the contact detection was set equal to $25N$ chosen by trial (the threshold is based on an estimated force). When the contact is detected, the wrench at the end-effector is smoothly adjusted to the desired wrench and the desired Cartesian

Fig. 2. Experimental Setup for Drilling Task

stiffness is accordingly adjusted. The planned variations are only present along the x direction of the task. Consequently, the robot maintains more compliant settings along the other directions, y and z . The modulation of the robot joint stiffness and damping follows a similar trend to realize the desired Cartesian stiffness. In fig. 3 (bottom) the plots show the main joints involved in the task execution with an higher impedance modulation value. In the both trials, the tracking error remains, fig. 3 (top-left), within the desired bounds of $0.03m$ dictated by the task requirements. Looking on the estimated forces, fig. 3 (top-right), it can be observed they display higher levels than the desired levels. This can be explained from the fact the desired contact force is rendered in an open loop manner (2). Then, higher contact forces will be generated if the motion propagation of the drilling is actually slower than the desired drilling trajectory (planned). Desired drilling trajectory of higher velocity will result in a higher tracking error and thus higher contact forces confirmed by looking at the tracking error and contact forces of the higher-velocity trial (light-blue lines) that are higher compared to those of the lower velocity execution (blue lines).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we presented a novel impedance planning framework capable of online modulating the impedance parameters of a robotic system based on the task requirements described in terms of the desired wrench and desired error at the end-effector. A varying Cartesian stiffness is then planned and realized by the robot while the stability is ensured by employing the Lyapunov direct method. The proposed impedance modulation was implemented on the CENTAURO robot and experimentally verified. Future works will focus on extending the presented impedance modulation method by incorporating a feedback correction action while safety with human operators will be maintained. This is expected to increase the robustness of the method, specifically to uncertainty adaptation.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 101016007 CONCERT and the Italian Fondo per la Crescita Sostenibile - Sportello "Fabbrica intelligente", PON I&C 2014 - 2020, project number F/190042/01-03/X44 RELAX.

Fig. 3. Drilling Task: the results of the experiments executed are shown in the above plots. The plots show a comparison between the execution of the task with two different execution time, 5s and 10s, represented by the light blue and blue lines, respectively. The bold dashed red line on the left denotes the start of the task. Top-Left: Trajectory Error (measured and planned), Top-Right (in order): Desired Cartesian Stiffness (planned) and Estimated Force (measured), Bottom-Left: Joints stiffness (planned), Bottom-Right: Joints Damping (planned).

REFERENCES

- [1] Hogan, Neville. "Impedance control: An approach to manipulation." 1984 American control conference. IEEE, 1984.
- [2] Lee, Jinoh, et al. "Upper-body impedance control with variable stiffness for a door opening task." 2014 IEEE-RAS International Conference on Humanoid Robots. IEEE, 2014.
- [3] Parent, David, Adrià Colomé, and Carme Torras. "Variable impedance control in Cartesian latent space while avoiding obstacles in null space." 2020 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA). IEEE, 2020.
- [4] Peternel, Luka, Tadej Petrič, and Jan Babič. "Human-in-the-loop approach for teaching robot assembly tasks using impedance control interface." 2015 IEEE international conference on robotics and automation (ICRA). IEEE, 2015.
- [5] Angelini, Franco, et al. "Online optimal impedance planning for legged robots." 2019 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS). IEEE, 2019.
- [6] Spyrakos-Papastavridis, Emmanouil, et al. "Online impedance parameter tuning for compliant biped balancing." 2015 IEEE-RAS 15th International Conference on Humanoid Robots (Humanoids). IEEE, 2015.
- [7] Ikeura, Ryojun, and Hikaru Inooka. "Variable impedance control of a robot for cooperation with a human." Proceedings of 1995 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation. Vol. 3. IEEE, 1995.
- [8] Ficuciello, Fanny, Luigi Villani, and Bruno Siciliano. "Variable impedance control of redundant manipulators for intuitive human-robot physical interaction." IEEE Transactions on Robotics 31.4 (2015): 850-863.
- [9] Kashiri, Navvab, et al. "CENTAURO: A hybrid locomotion and high power resilient manipulation platform." IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters 4.2 (2019): 1595-1602.
- [10] Albu-Schaffer, A., et al. "Soft robotics: what cartesian stiffness can obtain with passively compliant, uncoupled joints?." 2004 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)(IEEE Cat. No. 04CH37566). Vol. 4. IEEE, 2004.
- [11] Doornebosch, Luuk Maria, David A. Abbink, and Luka Peternel. "Analysis of coupling effect in human-commanded stiffness during bilateral tele-impedance." IEEE Transactions on Robotics 37.4 (2021): 1282-1297.
- [12] Ruscelli, Francesco, et al. "A fail-safe semi-centralized impedance controller: Validation on a parallel kinematics ankle." 2018 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS). IEEE, 2018.
- [13] Slotine, Jean-Jacques E., and Weiping Li. Applied nonlinear control. Vol. 199. No. 1. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice hall, 1991.